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DYNAMICS OF FLUORIDE ION RELEASE FROM TWO CONVENTIONAL GLAS-IONOMER CEMENTS: A COMPARATIVE STUDY

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Abstract:

The aim of this study was to comparatively present the dynamics of fluoride ion release from two conventional glass-ionomer cements. Material and Methods: FUJI IX (GC, Tokyo, Japan) and Ketac Molar (3M/ESPE, St. Paul, MN, USA) were used in the research. Ten discs with a diameter of 10mm and a thickness of 2mm were prepared for each material (n=5) according to the manufacturer's protocol. The samples were stored at 37°C and 100% humidity for 1 hour to allow the material to set. The samples were then immersed in 10ml of a solution of distilled water and TISAB III buffer in a 10:1 ratio. Analysis was performed using an ion chromatography test. The amount of released fluorides was recorded after 24h, 72h, 7 and 14 days, and statistical analysis was performed using a one-way ANOVA test, with a significance level of $p < 0.05$. Results: Total fluoride release was higher for FUJI ($13.35 \pm 3.2 \text{ mg/l}$) compared to Ketac ($9.1 \pm 3.1 \text{ mg/l}$) but without statistical significance. The release of fluoride in both materials was most intense in the first 24 hours, after which there was a lower growth of ion release, with almost stagnation reached on the 14th day for both materials. FUJI showed higher fluoride release than Ketac at all time points, but without statistical significance. The difference in fluoride release between first, third and seventh day on one hand and the 14th day on the other hand, for both materials, was statistically significant, while there was no statistical significance between the other time points. Conclusion: Both tested materials showed the most intense release of ions in the first 24 hours, while the intensity of ion release decreased over time. FUJI showed a higher degree of ion release than KETAC at all time points.

Key words: Glass-ionomer cement; fluorides; ion release